
Tista Tourism Village's Development towards Quality and Sustainable Tourism in Tabanan Regency

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ABSTRACT: Tourist sustainable concept become consideration in countries around the world to reach Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's). Development tourist sustainable become base development tourism in utilise nor in enjoy potency natural or environment without ruin it. One form implementation tourist sustainable is development village tourism. Tista Tourism Village is one of them village tourism in Tabanan Regency which implements it development tourism in rural areas going to quality and sustainable, where the community look after their village in a way good and full consciousness, so plan development housing area from investor to fail because not get agreement from society. Community industry growing, awareness public to tourist increase, preservation nature and culture walk in a way significant. A qualitative approach reinforced with focus group discussions was used to determine the implementation of quality and sustainable tourism village management and development as well as the active participation of the community in monitoring and evaluating the implementation of quality and sustainable tourism village development. The results of data analysis are displayed descriptively qualitatively and in the form of instruments for assessing quality and sustainable tourism villages. This research resulting in 7 tourism program implementations quality and sustainable, namely: implementation village tourism attractions, implementation village tourism amenities, implementation village tourism accessibility, implementation village tourism management, implementation human resources at village tourism, implementation business in the village tourism, and implementation village tourism marketing, as well generated instrument evaluation implementation development quality and sustainable tourism.

KEYWORD: Tourism Village, Community Participation, Quality Tourism, Sustainable Tourism

INTRODUCTION

Tourist sustainable concept become consideration in countries around the world to reach Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's). Development tourist sustainable become base development tourism in utilise nor in enjoy potency natural or environment without ruin it. Development tourist become sector development important to increase economy public because bring up multiplier effect direct or indirect [1].

Tourist have advantages other, besides from profit economic, such as: increase quality environment, improvement mark socio-cultural, becoming part from identity, can expand friendship, and also can create world peace [2]. Based on Constitution Number: 10 of 2009 Concerning Tourism mention that development tourism developed based on principle benefits, kinship, fairness and equality, balance, independence, sustainability, participatory, democratic, equality and unity [3].

Over time there has been a change in the tourism development paradigm, where the paradigm development tourist the majority focus on profits economy and bringing in traveler as much as possible, thus ignoring other aspects that are not always linear with development physical, such as: environment aspect, culture, traditions and customs in an area will have a detrimental impact on the natural, social and cultural environment [4]. Tourism development that is said to be successful is not only that which can accelerate economic growth, but also must ensure sustainability natural, social, cultural, tradition, daily life society, as well provision field work for society, so the concept of being guidelines in minimize impact negative development tourist is tourist sustainable concept [5].

One of the regency in Bali whose tourism development is well known is Tabanan Regency. Tabanan Regency has area 839.33 km² (14,90% of wide Bali Island) which has the potential is very complete, namely: mountains, lakes, rivers, and beaches.

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Tabanan Regency is also known as the rice granary of Bali Island which has the largest rice field area in Bali, namely: $\pm$ 460 ha with life public still agrarian dominant with subak system, cultural and spiritual life, as well the artistic spirit of the people is very high, so it becomes a special attraction for tourists [6].

Tabanan Regency has 27 villages existing tourism village has a Regent's Decree spread across 10 existing sub-districts, one tourism village with the advanced tourism village category in Tabanan Regency is Tista Tourism Village. Tista Village was designated as a tourist village by the Regent of Tabanan Number: 180/319/03/HK & HAM/2016, October 26, 2016, in addition to that, the Tista Village Tourism Awareness Group was also designated by the Regent of Tabanan Number: 180/27403/ HK & HAM/2016, September 19, 2016. Tista Village consists of four banjar, namely: Banjar Dangin Pangkung, Banjar Dauh Pangkung, Banjar Carik, and Banjar Lebah. Located in a lowland area that is slightly undulating, high from surface sea $\pm$ 3 m, temperature the air ranges from 27°C to 40°C. Tista Village has wide land 52.00 ha, with details rice field area 32.99 ha, land yard 7.03 ha, and field land 11.98 ha and most of the people of Tista Village still rely on farming for their livelihood because it is still an agricultural area [7].

The people of Tista Village are very supportive on their village become village tourism, this has resulted in the development of Tista Tourism Village getting better and even getting the advanced tourism village category in Tabanan Regency [8]. Implementation as tourism village is community look after their village in a way good and full consciousness, so plan development housing in Tista Tourism Village from investors to fail because did not receive approval from society. On the other hand, community industry growing, awareness public to tourist increase, preservation nature and culture walk in a way significant. Even when pandemic, the community continues to carry out structuring and maintenance activities for tourist attractions in the Tista Tourism Village.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tourism Villages

Tourism villages are rural areas that include an atmosphere of rural authenticity in socio-economic, socio-cultural life, customs, daily life of the community, building architecture, including distinctive spatial structures, unique community economic activities, as well as great potential for managing and developing various components. tourism, such as: homestays, tourist activities, culinary and other tourism needs [9]. Tourism villages can also be used defined as a form harmonious integration between attractions tourism, accommodation and tourist facilities are presented in the lifestyle of rural communities that are integrated with the prevailing culture and traditional procedures [10].

Sustainable Tourism

Principles development sustainable tourism based on environmental, economic and socio-cultural development in tourism towards an appropriate balance to ensure long-term program sustainability. Thus, sustainable tourism must: 1) Make optimal use of environmental resources in tourism development; 2) Respect the socio-cultural authenticity of the local community as the host; and 3) Guaranteeing feasibility, long-term economic management, providing equitable social economic benefits, income-earning opportunities, and social services to local host communities, as well as contributing to poverty alleviation efforts [11].

Monitoring and Evaluation

Success in achieving goals is half determined by the plan that has been set and half by the supervision or monitoring function [12]. Monitoring aims to determine the suitability and accuracy of activities with the plans that have been prepared, including correcting activities that deviate from the plan, correcting misuse of rules, and ensuring that goals can be achieved. Evaluation is one of the management functions carried out on all or some of the program elements and program implementation. Evaluation is carried out continuously, periodically, and at any time before, during, and after the program is implemented. It is important to carry out evaluations to find out whether the goals that have been set have been achieved, whether they are in accordance with the plan, and what the impact will be after the program is implemented [13].

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Determination Technique Informant

Determining informants was carried out using a purposive sampling technique to obtain the accuracy and reliability of data that can be tested for validity and credibility, where informants know the depth of information related to the problem being researched and they can be accepted by various groups related to management and have tourism knowledge [14].

The key informants in this research are figures who are considered to know about the object of the research being carried out. These figures are: Village Head, Traditional Village Leader, Tourism Awareness Group Leader, Regional Head, Community Figures, and the Tourism Industry.

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Sample Determination Technique

In this research, the samples were the Tista Village community using the Quota Sampling Method, namely a sampling technique by taking a predetermined number of samples. The sampling technique in this research refers to the Slovin Formula [15] which states that

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Description: N: Number Population

n: Number of Samples

e: Error Rate

Samples used is as much 100 people. The data collection methods used in this research are:

1) Observation; 2) In-depth interview; 3) Questionnaire; 4) Literature Study; and 5) Focus Group Discussion [16].

DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

The data that has been collected will be analyzed using several techniques, as follows:

1. Qualitative Descriptive Analysis

Data analysis is the process of organizing and sorting them into patterns, categories and basic units of description, so that themes can be found and working hypotheses can be formulated, as suggested by the data [17]. By using qualitative descriptive analysis, namely describing a phenomenon and then linking it with other phenomena through interpretation to describe it in a quality that is close to reality [18].

2. Literature Study Analysis

Literature study is a data analysis technique for reviewing books, literature searches, notes and reports related to research. This literature study supports valid data sources and an assessment of the concepts and theories used is carried out based on the available literature. Literature review also functions in building concepts or theories that become the scientific basis for research, so that using this method can solve the problem being studied [19].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of a Quality and Sustainable Tourism Program in Tista Tourism Village, Tabanan Regency

The expected tourism development is tourism that is able to attract quality tourists to provide high foreign exchange and also encourage economic growth in a region [20]. Quality tourism is the focus of tourism development to grow the creative economy and national economic resilience through quality tourism. Apart from that, good and significant tourism growth has a positive impact, so the development of sustainable tourism is also a priority in order to protect and preserve crucial potential or resources, both for the present and the future.

One of the tourism village that applies the concept of quality and sustainable tourism is Tista Tourism Village, Kerambitan District, Tabanan Regency. Activity programs that support the management and development of quality and sustainable tourism in Tista Tourism Village, Tabanan Regency which have been directly implemented by the Tista community are as follows:

Tourist Village Attraction

Tista Tourism Village, Kerambitan District, Tabanan Regency has various attractions which become tourism products or tourist packages that are served or displayed to visitors or visiting tourists. These attractions are real implementations that are already underway in the management and development activities of the Tista Tourism Village and with the support of the Tista community. The implementation of the Tista tourist attraction can be conveyed as follows:

1. Natural attraction, where the Tista Village area is still a vast expanse of rice fields and community plantations with a subak system that is still very good. There is also the Beji Temple which is a water source that is used by the community, both for spiritual purposes and for the community's daily needs, where the Beji water has been tested by the relevant agencies and the results are extraordinary because it contains important minerals that are really needed by the body, so that the water can be drunk directly. There is also a river which can attract visitors and tourists as well as a very peaceful atmosphere in the Tista Village environment.

2. Selfie activities, the natural atmosphere and harmony of life in the Tista Tourism Village attract visitors to carry out tourist activities and are also used to take selfies at photo spots that are directly chosen by visitors according to their tastes and conscience. There is also a photo spot in the middle of the rice fields near Batu Gede (natural big stone) which has been prepared by the management for visitors and tourists who want to take selfies.

3. The natural environment in Tista Tourism Village is very beautiful. Tourism awareness are widely understood by the people of Tista Village become tourism village. Environmental arrangements are consciously and independently carried out by the people of Tista Village, so that the beauty and beauty of the natural environment in Tista Tourism Village is cumulatively created.

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These activities can add to the cool, comfortable, peaceful and harmonious atmosphere in Tista Village which of course will add to the attraction of Tista Tourism Village.

4. The Tista Festival is an annual festival held in Tista Tourism Village which displays the various potentials of Tista Village, such as: artistic and cultural potential, culinary potential, local agricultural products from Tista Village, and unique creativity from the people of Tista Village. This festival aims to foster a spirit of togetherness and an expression of community pride in the potential of Tista Village and to promote the tourism potential of Tista Tourism Village, which is very diverse and unique and has its own characteristics, so that tourists have alternative tourist visits to Tista Tourism Village.

Tourism Village Amenities

Tourists in carrying out tourism activities really need the availability of facilities to support their travel and provide various conveniences for tourists to improve their travel experience. The more complete a destination has in terms of amenities, the more tourists will visit. The facilities available at Tista Tourism Village are as follows:

1. Adequate toilets and parking areas for visitors and tourists visiting Tista Tourism Village, so as to provide comfort and ease of travel.

2. There are adequate homestays available in the Tista Tourism Village, which is a requirement for the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village. Several people's houses have been used as homestays and are often used by tourists to stay overnight. The existence of this homestay is also an indicator that community support for the development of Tista Tourism Village is very large and can provide direct benefits to the people of Tista Village.

3. There is an adequate internet network in the Tista Village area which is the main access in terms of the rapid development of information today, where the digital world and global information is very massive and requires the availability of an adequate internet network. In Tista Tourism Village, this is a priority, not only for tourism needs but also for the needs of the Tista Village community for access to information and communication.

4. Health facilities are supported in the Tista Tourism Village as a form of health insurance for visitors and tourists who visit because they are anticipatory steps if things related to health occur. This is also the right recommendation for visiting Tista Tourism Village.

Tourism Villages Accessibility

Accessibility also means everything that can make it easy for tourists to visit a tourist destination [21]. An area will be visited a lot because of the availability of road infrastructure, close to the airport, and available transportation to get to the tourist destination area, so that the level of convenience greatly influences the development of the tourist destination area. Accessibility conditions in Tista Tourism Village are as follows:

1. Safe and adequate road access in Tista Tourism Village. The roads in Tista Tourism Village is in a good condition, so they can be passed by vehicles, both two-wheeled vehicles and cars. Including the roads to the banjars are very good and smooth. Also, the roads that connect to the Tista Tourism Village are in very good condition, which is one of the strengths of the development of the Tista Tourism Village because of its ease of access and ease of reach.

2. Road conditions are also safe for pedestrians and people with disabilities because on average the topography of Tista Village is flat, making it easier for pedestrians and people with disabilities. It is also supported by roads in Tista Village which are not too congested with vehicles, so it is also safe to carry out jogging and trekking activities while enjoying the natural beauty of Tista Village and seeing firsthand the daily life of the people of Tista Village.

3. Ease of services and information sources which are demands in the current era of globalization and information openness, so that the use of social media, websites and WA groups is very easy and internet access is also very good which makes it possible to use all existing online media for the benefit of development of Tista Tourism Village.

Tourism Village Management

The aim of management is to mobilize all existing resources, such as: human resources and facilities in an organization, so as to avoid wasting time, energy and material in achieving set goals, maintain balance between goals that are less aligned, and to achieve efficiency and work effectiveness. The management of Tista Tourism Village carried out by managers with various businesses is as follows:

1. Tourism awareness group collaboration with official villages, traditional villages, stakeholders and the government. The approach taken by Tourism awareness group in developing the Tista Tourism Village is carried out with various parties, where support, input, cooperation from related parties will be of great benefit in preparing all the needs and requirements for managing and developing the tourist village, such as: training, promotional cooperation and marketing, regulations, preparing products and tour packages, creating harmonization and good communication in the Tista Village area, and so on. This collaboration will open up opportunities for the process of maturing the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village. The structure of the

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tourist village management organization has been carried out according to its duties and functions, so that the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village can continue to run according to the targets and objectives to be achieved as stated in the work program or activity program.

2. Regular meetings are held by the village government, tourism awareness group and institutions in Tista Village. Meetings are regularly held to discuss the development of the Tista Tourism Village to determine progress in terms of activities and evaluate the activities carried out because the objects and subjects in the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village are all the potential and resources that exist in Tista Village. Thus, joint monitoring and evaluation is always held.

3. Complaints from the community are accepted and resolved in a friendly manner. Tourism awareness group in this case is very open to receiving various suggestions, input, and even complaints from the community regarding the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village. This can be a trigger and driver for tourism awareness group to always be able to improve their abilities and make improvements, so that from day to day they always show progress. The active role of the community will also be a very effective control in the management and development process because they will be able to direct it according to the work programs that have been prepared and ultimately the aim of developing the Tista Tourism Village is to create prosperity in the community.

4. There are clear programs. Tourism awareness group in carrying out its duties and functions follows a work program that has been prepared and mutually agreed upon. This work program is the reference and basis for the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village, so that the activities carried out by the tourism awareness group can assess and measure the level of performance and level of progress. The community can monitor all activities and activities carried out as well as provide effective control. This is important to ensure effectiveness and conformity with the work program that has been formulated and outlined together, so that the development of the Tista Tourism Village is in accordance with shared goals and expectations.

5. Good and transparent funding management from the manager in managing funding for the development of the Tista Tourism Village. This funding comes from village funds which are used well and delivered transparently to create quality and sustainable management and development. This pattern can foster high levels of public trust. This capital is what makes community participation and support in the management and development of Tista Tourism Village also high.

6. There is already a set of legal regulations in the form of Village Regulations which regulate, protect and maintain social, security, economic and community stability. The village regulation as one of the regulations that serves as a basis, especially in the management and development of tourist villages, has been prepared in Tista Village through joint deliberation and input from various parties. Through the basis and foundation of the Village Regulation, the implementation of the work program and the limitations that must be adhered to are clearly regulated in the Village Regulation. This village regulation can also provide guarantees for the quality and sustainable management and development of the Tista Tourism Village as well as creating stability and harmonization of social relations in the community and can create a good and conducive climate for improving the community's economy.

7. Continuous improvement in the quality and competency of human resources through training programs, both training held in Tista Village itself and training carried out by other parties, such as: regency and provincial tourism offices, as well as from related ministries. Assistance is also often provided in Tista Tourism Village, such as: from universities, industry, and also from other related institutions. These various activities and activities can significantly increase the knowledge, skills and competence of the community, in the tourism sector and in other fields in supporting the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village. In addition, increasing community competence is very helpful in increasing community motivation, innovation and creativity in creating and packaging new products and creating employment opportunities that provide economic benefits for the community, so that the resources owned by Tista Village are always maintained and cared for. with the daily life needs of the Tista community which also becomes a tourist attraction in the Tista Tourism Village which provides profit added value in supporting the local economy of the community in Tista Village.

Tourism Village Human Resources

Human resources capacity that is oriented towards knowledge and skills will determine whether a person is successful or not in completing the assigned work optimally. Human resources have an important role in every organizational activity and need to be supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure as well as financial sources to achieve planned goals. The improvement and development of human resources in Tista Tourism Village is as follows:

1. Build communication and discuss with the community. One way to get input and suggestions is to always communicate and discuss with the community. This input or suggestion can be used as a point in assessing and preparing things that are needed or that need to be improved. To further prepare programs that lead to increasing capabilities and competencies in the tourism sector, both for managers and for the Tista Village Community. The programs prepared will certainly provide equal opportunities to the community through scheduling that is adjusted to the time of training, including mentoring programs from related parties.

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2. The people of Tista Village welcome tourists who visit Tista Tourism Village. This is an important asset in the future development of the Tista Tourism Village, where with good and friendly reception from the community towards visitors and tourists, they will feel safe and comfortable to come to visit and feel at home.

3. Many of the younger generation of Tista are graduates of tourism schools and even university level. It is these future generations who will further improve the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village because they have been equipped with specific knowledge and skills related to tourism from school and college. The parents in Tista Village are also very enthusiastic and have a high level of awareness to send their children to school, at least up to secondary school, which is of course a very large capital in preparing superior human resources for the quality and sustainable management and development of Tista Tourism Village.

4. In general, with the existence of the Tista Tourism Village, the community is very supportive and feels the economic results and benefits, changes in behavior regarding cleanliness and environmental preservation, as well as culture and customs, so it is important to further improve and spur the management and development of the Tista Tourism Village in accordance with potential and resources to achieve a quality and sustainable tourism village. This difficult task will become lighter if synergies and cooperation and good communication are maintained between competent and related parties, components and institutions for mutual interests and mutual benefits.

Business in Tourism Villages

Tourism business is an activity that aims to provide tourism services by providing or operating tourist attractions, tourism facility businesses, and other businesses related to the tourism sector. The growth and development of business or industry in Tista Tourism Village can be described as follows:

1. Village owned enterprises and village financial institutions provide capital. To develop small and medium businesses in the community which are home industries, initial capital is needed to open a business to prepare materials and other needs. Village financial institution prepares capital for people starting their businesses and village owned enterprises will accommodate products cultivated by the community. This synergy will open up opportunities for people to start home businesses which will help improve the local economy of the people in Tista Village. In the future, these businesses will also be able to use local materials produced in Tista Village, so that the prices of these products will increase and farmers will be more enthusiastic about cultivating and planting their rice fields which are the majority of their livelihoods staple of society. This will make the post-harvest efforts of the community in Tista Village more effective and implemented.

2. Guidance and assistance from related agencies and universities. The people of Tista Village have often received guidance and assistance from related parties in terms of improving business or industry in the community. Various types of training and mentoring related to products to promotional and marketing techniques have often been held, so that the people of Tista Village already have various knowledge and skills regarding business development or community industry. This also encourages the growth and development of industry in society which can increase and stimulate economic activities in society. Various crafts, food processing and other economic activities are starting to grow in Tista Village which also supports the management and development of Tista Tourism Village in terms of preparing local souvenirs.

Tourism Village Marketing

Marketing seeks to create and exchange products, both goods and services to consumers based on market needs and desires [22]. Various marketing efforts carried out in Tista Tourism Village are as follows:

1. Hold marketing collaboration with various parties, such as: with several travel agencies, collaborating with other tourist villages, joining the tourist village network, and collaborating with star-ups that promote and market tourist village products. By holding this collaboration, the management will automatically prepare superior products or packages that will be promoted and marketed, so that they will be able to attract visitors and tourists to come to Tista Tourism Village. All facilities and human resources in the community also need to be well prepared to welcome and provide excellent service to visitors and tourists visiting Tista Tourism Village.

2. Promotion and marketing are further optimized through digital marketing which uses various online media, such as: website, youtube, facebook, instagram, whatsapp, and so on. It is hoped that this promotion using various online media will be able to further introduce the Tista Tourism Village with its various attractions, uniqueness and characteristics that tourists, both domestic and foreign tourists, need to visit. The consequence of this promotion is that you have to keep updating the promotional content so that it is always updated, so that the information provided is the latest and most up-to-date information.

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Implementation Evaluation as Monitoring and Evaluation Reference Tourism Quality and Sustainable in Tista Tourism Village, Tabanan Regency

Monitoring and evaluation are an important part of management activities (planning, organizing, actuating and controlling), where these activities aim to determine the suitability between the plans that have been set and the results that have been achieved through regular activities or programs. If problems or obstacles are discovered during implementation, improvements and even improvements can be made immediately.

Monitoring is a process of analyzing information based on indicators that have been determined systematically and continuously for an activity to ensure that an activity runs according to plan. Evaluation is a process of measuring and assessing objectively and validly the services that have been provided so that their implementation runs effectively and efficiently. Monitoring indicators include the essence of activities and targets set in program planning as well as input in conducting evaluations [23].

As a reference in the implementation of quality and sustainable tourism in Tista Tourism Village, Tabanan Regency and also as a reference for monitoring and evaluation assessments of the management and development of quality and sustainable tourism in general, both for the management and development of tourism village, tourist destinations and tourist attractions, a quality and sustainable tourism implementation assessment instrument was created which can also be used to assess and measure implementation in the field, whether or not assistance from related parties is needed, and is already in the quality and sustainable category, so that it can be a guide for tourism management and development in other places, as well as as an assessment instrument for a village before registering it as a tourism village. For more details regarding the reference for assessing the implementation of quality and sustainable tourism, see the instrument below.

Monitoring and Evaluation Assessment References for the Implementation of Quality and Sustainable Tourism in the Tista Tourism Village

NO.	VARIABLES	INDICATOR	SCORE
1.	TOURISM VILLAGE ATTRACTION	Creation and management product based local	3
		Diversification product tour	2
		There is cycle repeat product tour	2
		Enhancement visits and length of stay traveler	2
		Continuity events and packages tour	3
2.	TOURISM VILLAGE AMENITIES	Enhancement quality environment (available system management waste and processing trash)	3
		Resident 's house used as homestay	3
		Use and development architecture traditional	2
		There is quantity and quality toilet	2
		There is a traditional market	2
		Available land adequate parking	2
3.	TOURISM VILLAGE ACCESSIBILITY	There is access safe and adequate roads	2
		Provision of conditions road village safe for pedestrian	3
		Convenience access for disabled person disability	2
		Convenience services and resources information	2
		Openness host to traveler	3
4.	TOURISM VILLAGE MANAGEMENT	There is a meeting routine agenda	3
		There are clear programs	3
		Harmonization coordination between institution	3
		There is systematic reception complaints and resolution problem	3
		Management good and transparent funding	3
		Good and efficient cooperation pattern with stakeholders	2

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5.	TOURISM VILLAGE HUMAN RESOURCES	There are community age productive and graduates tourism school	2
		Enhancement competence community in the field tourist	3
		Strengthening community participation	3
		Creation field work local	3
		Maintain and preserve inheritance local culture	3
6.	BUSINESS IN A TOURISM VILLAGE	Enhancement home industry	3
		Provision and convenience of community business capital	2
		There is influence from existing community businesses	3
		Prioritize material standard results community product	3
		Mentoring and coaching continuity community business	2
7.	TOURISM VILLAGE MARKETING	Strengthening promotion as well as marketing products and packages tourism village	3
		Effective and efficient marketing cooperation _	3
		Create <i>branding</i> tourism village	3
		Strengthening human resources marketing	3
		Setup adequate internet network	3
		Expand and strengthen media and channels marketing	3

This instrument consists of 7 variables, where in each variable there are 5 to 6 indicators which become a reference for assessment in the form of a score value of 1 to 3, where the total number of indicators available is 38 indicators. The total score prepared in this instrument is 100 (one hundred), where the number 100 is the ideal number to describe the implementation of quality and sustainable tourism management and development. The meaning of the score values listed in this instrument is as follows:

1. A value of 1 means Very Poor (even non-existent),
2. A score of 2 means Adequate (but there is), and
3. A value of 3 means Very Important (required).

In the assessment trials carried out at several tourism attractions and tourism villages, different score values were obtained, so that to be able to see the position or category of the object being assessed, you can see the range and meaning of the score values as below:

1. Score range 0 – 33, meaning the tourism village has stopped,
2. Score range 34 – 75, meaning tourism village need assistance,
3. Score range 76 – 100, meaning a quality and sustainable tourism village.

With this assessment instrument, of course it will be able to help to take appropriate steps in evaluating the management and development of tourism attractions, tourism destinations and tourism village, so that appropriate policies or programs can be developed from stakeholders as well as a self-evaluation of management and development of each tourism attraction, tourism destination and tourism village, so that there is a reference or guideline in making future plans, strategies and programs.

CONCLUSION

From the results of this presentation, it can be concluded that the progress of Tista Tourism Village towards quality and sustainable tourism in Tabanan Regency is as follows:

1. Implementation of quality and sustainable tourism programs in Tista Tourism Village, Tabanan Regency, namely: 1) Implementation of tourism village attractions, including: natural attractions, selfie activities, the natural environment in Tista Tourism Village is very beautiful, and the Tista Festival; 2) Implementation of tourism village amenities, including: toilets and parking lots, adequate homestays available, adequate internet network and adequate health facilities; 3) Implementation of tourism village accessibility, including: safe and adequate road access, safe road conditions for pedestrians, and ease of services and information sources; 4) Implementation of tourism village management, including: tourism awareness group collaboration with other related parties, holding regular meetings in tourism village, receiving various complaints from the community and at the same

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time looking for solutions, having a clear development program, good and transparent funding management, already having a Village Tourism Regulation, and always paying attention to improving the quality and competency of human resources; 5) Implementation of tourism village human resources, including: building communication and discussions with the community, the community welcomes tourists who visit, many of the young generation of Tista are tourism school graduates, always maintain and preserve local culture, and strongly support the development of the Tista Tourism Village; 6) Business implementation in tourist villages, including: village owned enterprises and village financial institutions which provide capital and guidance and assistance from related agencies and universities; and 7) Implementation of tourism village marketing, including: marketing collaboration with various parties and marketing through digital marketing.

2. Implementation of assessment as a reference for monitoring and evaluating quality and sustainable tourism in Tista Tourism Village, Tabanan Regency, namely: producing an assessment instrument consisting of 7 variables, where in each variable there are 5 to 6 indicators which become a reference for assessment in the form score value 1 to 3, where the total existing indicators are 38 indicators. The total score prepared in this instrument is 100 (one hundred), where the number 100 is the ideal number to describe the implementation of quality and sustainable tourism management and development. In the assessment trials carried out at several tourism attractions and tourism villages, a number of different score values were obtained, so that to be able to see the position or category of the object being assessed, you can see the range and meaning of the score values 0 – 33, meaning the tourist village has stopped, score 34 – 75, meaning a tourism village need assistance, and a score of 76 – 100, meaning a quality and sustainable tourism village.

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